

An MAC Probability Assessment Framework for Integrated Operations in Urban Air Mobility Considering Safety Barriers

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Abstract—Risk assessment is a key issue in enabling the increasing use of unmanned aircraft systems (UAS), especially in integrated operational urban airspace. This paper proposes a method to systematically quantify the mid-air collision (MAC) risk for different types of aircraft in urban air mobility (UAM). Specifically, a novel assessment framework is formulated that includes three timelines to track risk evolution for different aircraft (i.e., cooperative, non-cooperative and manned aircraft) and four safety barriers (i.e., procedural, strategic, tactical, and collision avoidance mitigation) to prevent a conflict ending in MAC. Guided by the framework, analytical models are established considering trajectory uncertainty, latency time, and detection and avoidance (DAA) system risk ratio to calculate the failure probability of each barrier, and thus an overall MAC probability. This paper concludes with a real-world case study demonstrating the effectiveness of proposed method. Results show that the cooperative UAS contributes the highest MAC risk in an integrated environment, and the MAC risk posed by manned aircraft spikes when the ownship is approximately 4200 meters from the airport area, while the non-collaborative UAS maintain a consistent minimal MAC risk.

Keywords—Urban Air Mobility; Mid-Air Collision; Safety Assessment; Mitigation Measures

I. INTRODUCTION

Unmanned aircraft systems (UAS) have been widely used in low-altitude urban airspace for various tasks due to the advantages of flexibility, convenience, and low cost [1], [2]. Following this trend, the urban airspace system is gradually evolving from manned aviation through hybrid operations with UAS to eventually integrated operations. These new entrants have increased the density and complexity of the airspace, which means that effectively guaranteeing the operational safety of the aircraft has become the critical problem facing the development of UAM. The primary challenge is to accurately assess the mid-air collision (MAC) risk, which is a prerequisite for conflict resolution techniques and a key component of urban air traffic management. In particular, in the integrated operational environment, where aircraft may face multiple sources for collision risks, including cooperative UAS, non-cooperative UAS, and manned aircraft, resulting in serious hazards to other aircraft, as well as people and infrastructure on the ground.

In the literature, the risk assessment of UAS with other UAS or manned aircraft has been extensively studied. Some

scholars further divide UAS into cooperative UAS and non-cooperative UAS. The flight information of cooperative UAS is publicly available or the supervisory authorities can query or record their flight trajectories. In contrast, the information of non-cooperative UAS can only be detected directly by some sensors like radar and their flight intentions cannot be perceived, so there are different MAC assessment methods for these two types of UAS. For cooperative UAS, existing approaches can be divided into two categories: geometric conflict methods and probabilistic calculation methods. Mercado et al. [3] improve the classical geometric conflict methods based on vehicle intention information and propose an analytical mathematical form to judge the speed obstacle and detect the risk of conflict. Paielli et al. [4] propose a mathematical analysis method to estimate the probability of conflict efficiently for aircraft pairs in free flight. For non-cooperative UAS, most of the current research has focused on Monte Carlo and gas models. Wang et al. [5] use a Monte Carlo model to simulate the worst-case flight path of a non-cooperative intruder (moving directly toward the aircraft) and calculate the MAC probability. Su et al. [6] treat non-cooperative UAS as randomly distributed air molecules and estimate the probability that an aircraft will be intruded.

For MAC assessment of manned aircraft, the Monte Carlo simulation is still the main method. Pothana et al. [7] fits the velocity, heading, and altitude of UAS using a Gaussian distribution and determines the MAC risk near the airport by comparing the possible position of UAS with the historical ADS-B data from manned aircraft. Wang, et al. [8] constructs a 3-D Monte Carlo positional distribution model based on the flight dynamics of UAS, so as to establish an alert zone boundaries around the airport.

The above methods characterize the MAC probability from different perspectives such as mathematical statistics and geometric relations, but the common drawback is that they treat the risk as a process of continuous deterioration and do not take into account mitigation measures in actual operations. The specific operations risk assessment (SORA) approach provides clear guidelines for assessing operational risks [9], which identifies the sources and consequences that lead to both air and ground risks. Some scholars have conducted research on low-altitude operations based on SORA, such

as determining separation minima [10] and designing flight procedures [11]. However, SORA is a qualitative method that only classifies the collision risk from manned aircraft in terms of air risk, based only on the proximity to aerodromes and controlled airspace volumes, while lacking a specific metric for quantifying the level of safety. In previous work [12], we proposed a quantitative method by introducing a "collision probability per flight time" metric based on SORA. However, this method is limited to assessing risks for cooperative UAS and does not consider other risk sources or corresponding mitigation measures in the integrated airspace, thus requiring further improvement.

To address the research gaps mentioned above, it is necessary to systematically analyze the evolution law of MAC risk for different types of aircraft, and to explore the multi-level risk mitigation measures and their failure causes throughout the process, so as to form a comprehensive risk assessment methodology. As a result, the main contributions of this paper are summarized as follows:

- A comprehensive MAC probability assessment framework applicable to multi-type aircraft is proposed, including cooperative UAS, non-cooperative UAS, and manned aircraft, which enhances the SORA method by extending its air risk scope beyond the conventional manned aircraft.
- Three MAC evolution timelines designated to multi-type aircraft are formulated, covering four main safety barriers for preventing a conflict ending in a MAC. This leads to a careful MAC probability prediction considering all barriers have failed, which delves the SORA method by providing quantitative justifications.
- For safety barriers, errors due to various external factors are incorporated into an analytical solution of conflict probability to quickly determine whether a UAS poses a threat. Also, multiple maneuver strategies and a latency time determination function are established to further improve the accuracy of the results.

II. FRAMEWORK

The scenario considered in this paper is an integrated operation with more efficiency in the future, in which cooperative UAS navigate through dynamic corridor, environmental uncertainties may lead to potential spatial and temporal overlaps among them. Furthermore, the corridors may also be intruded by non-cooperative UAS and manned aircraft. Consequently, aircraft operating in such airspace will face MAC risk from multiple aircraft types, including cooperative UAS, non-cooperative UAS, and manned aircraft. Therefore, a comprehensive assessment framework applicable to multi-type aircraft is modeled after the Swiss-Cheese model [13], as shown in Fig. 1, which views MAC as the detrimental result of the simultaneous failure of multiple defense measures, further categorized into the failure of procedural mitigation, strategic mitigation, tactical mitigation, and collision avoidance.

Procedural mitigation measures are developed during the airspace planning phase, mainly through mandatory measures such as airspace segregation or corridor limits to prohibit the entry of UAS into essential areas. However, the presence of

non-cooperative UAS or the untimely opening of corridors often leads to accidental intrusion events, which are the main reasons why procedural mitigation measures may fail.

Strategic mitigation measures are applied before the flight, primarily utilizing flight trajectory planning and authorization to avoid temporal or spatial overlap of UAS pairs embedded in operational intents. The main reasons for strategic mitigation failure are the operational uncertainties during the flight, such as wind influence, navigation error, flight technical error, which may cause the trajectory offset, and then the situation of tactical conflict.

Tactical mitigation measures refer to the tactical separation resolution provided by actors such as UTM service supplier (USS) or U-Space Service Provider (USSP). When receiving the warning of strategic mitigation failure, they can issue maneuver advisories or instructions to the aircraft to avoid the loss of well-clear (LOWC) situation. However, executing maneuvers requires response time (i.e., latency time) due to some reasons such as pilot reaction and communication transmission time. If the aircraft's predicted approach time to the DAA well-clear (DWC) volume is less than that time (i.e., the aircraft enters the DWC before it has time to complete the maneuver), tactical mitigation failure will occur.

Collision avoidance is the next mitigation barrier during flight, mainly for the measures provided by the onboard DAA system, which is initiated immediately by the onboard flight computer when tactical mitigation measures have failed. Due to the close distance between an aircraft pair at that moment and the endogenous malfunction probability of the DAA system, this measure also has the possibility of failure.

After collision avoidance failure, the two aircraft involved have reached the state of near mid-air collision (NMAC), the probability of such a NMAC developing into an actual collision at this point is subject to providence (P_{pro}). As the inability to accurately simulate "providence", we assume a worst-case scenario where a collision must occur if the collision avoidance fails, i.e. $P_{pro} = 1$ in such a case.

Based on the above framework, the MAC probability assessment processes in line with the specific evolution timelines for different types of aircraft are designed separately.

A. MAC Evolution Timeline for cooperative UAS

The origin of MAC risk between cooperative UAS is mainly a strategic conflict caused by operational uncertainty, which evolves into a series of subsequent risk events. The MAC evolution timeline connects the events that lead to MAC and identifies the failure signs for each barrier, which consists of three phases:

Phase 1: A conflict probability estimation model during encounter is proposed to characterize the probability of spatio-temporal overlap of UAS pairs due to uncertainty factors, i.e., strategic mitigation failure probability expressed by P_{ST}^{cop} . The encounter period is a key parameter in the model, we introduce a warning mechanism according to the detect and avoid alerting logic (DAIDALUS) [14], which specifies that a warning should be issued if intruders with constant velocities enter the DWC volume within 25 seconds. Consequently, we

Fig. 1. Overall framework for MAC probability assessment.

define the encounter period as 25 seconds and calculate the conflict probability between two UAS within this time scale.

Phase 2: After strategic mitigation fails, the ownship performs maneuvers according to the instructions to prevent the intruder from entering the collision envelope. This paper defines the concept of collision envelop as cylinder referring to the DWC volume in Ref [15]. A maximum approach time estimation model is established to estimate the time allowed to fly after receiving the strategic failure warning, and determine the tactical conflict mitigation failure probability P_{TC}^{cop} by comparing with the latency time.

Phase 3: The collision avoidance measures dominated by the airborne DAA system control the aircraft to avoid collision automatically, we summarize the endogenous failure rate by analyzing the historical data as the collision avoidance failure probability P_{CA}^{cop} . If this measure fails, the two UAS enter the NMAC and the MAC between them depends on providence.

Therefore, the MAC probability of ownship relative to cooperative UAS i is:

$$P_{cop-i} = P_{ST}^{cop-i} \cdot P_{TC}^{cop-i} \cdot P_{CA}^{cop-i} \cdot P_{pro-i} \quad (1)$$

Since the flight plan of cooperative UAS is known, the MAC risk associated with each individual UAS can be independently assessed, enabling the determination of MAC risk (p_{cop}) posed by all cooperative UAS within the airspace:

$$p_{cop} = 1 - \prod_{i=0}^n (1 - P_{cop-i}) \quad (2)$$

B. MAC Evolution Timeline for non-cooperative UAS

Due to unpredictability of non-cooperative UAS's movement trends, targeted mitigation is unfeasible after intrusion, the MAC evolution timeline for non-cooperative UAS involves only procedural mitigation strategies, i.e., airspace isolation measures. Furthermore, given the inability to precisely quantify the number of non-cooperative UAS intrusions, we establish a dynamic GAS model to quantify the probability of non-cooperative UAS intrusion $P_{PC}^{non-cop}$ during mission

execution from a global perspective, a MAC is considered to have occurred if this procedural mitigation measure fail, as shown in Eq. (3).

$$P_{non} = P_{PC}^{non} \cdot P_{pro} \quad (3)$$

C. MAC Evolution Timeline for manned aircraft

Manned aircraft are susceptible to UAS during the take-off and landing phases, so the first barrier to preventing MAC between UAS and manned aircraft is procedural mitigation measures, specifically through dynamic corridor management in integrated airspace to ensure temporal and spatial separation near terminal zones. We establish a GAS model based on the STAR and SID routes to characterize the procedural mitigation failure probability P_{PC}^{man} . If a UAS intrudes into the STAR and SID area during manned aircraft operations, the UAS will receive maneuver instructions (from USSP directly or ATC via USSP). This process can be summarized as tactical conflict mitigation, and the failure probability P_{TC}^{man} can be estimated using the maximum approach time estimation model, so the MAC probability with manned aircraft is:

$$P_{man} = P_{PC}^{man} \cdot P_{TC}^{man} \cdot P_{pro} \quad (4)$$

For integrated operation scenarios in urban air mobility, the risk source cannot be just one type of aircraft. From the perspective of ownship, it is necessary to assess the MAC probability caused by all aircraft in the airspace, i.e., overall MAC probability. This paper introduces a metric, namely "collision probability per flight time", to quantify the assessment result, which can be expressed as the superposition of the maximum risk value posed by the three types of aircraft during a fixed flight time, as shown in Eq. (5).

$$P_{all} = 1 - (1 - P_{cop}) \cdot (1 - P_{non}) \cdot (1 - P_{man}) \quad (5)$$

where P_{cop} , P_{non} , P_{man} represent the maximum value of MAC probability with cooperative UAS, non-cooperative UAS and manned aircraft in a time period.

III. METHODOLOGY

In this section, the MAC probability P_{cop}^i , $P_{non-cop}$ and P_{man} is modeled in detail. In the models, the ownship refers to the individual whose risk needs to be assessed, and the intruder refers to the individual causing the MAC risk. In addition, we use a cylinder region to model ownship's collision envelope, and the range parameter is taken as $R_{en} = 2000ft$ and $H_{en} = 250ft$ according to Ref [15], where (R_{en}, H_{en}) are the radius and the half of height of collision envelope.

To clarify, this section relies on the following assumptions:

- During the approach of the aircraft and the intruder, the aircraft remains in level flight and the relative velocity and direction of the aircraft are constant.
- When an aircraft maneuvers to avoid collision, only one maneuver strategy is selected, and the combinations of multiple maneuver strategies are not considered.
- The ownship is responsible to perform the avoidance maneuver when facing a intruder.

A. MAC Probability Assessment for Cooperative UAS

This section describes the process of modeling MAC probabilities for cooperative UAS. we first introduce how to assess the conflict probability during encounter, which is regarded as the strategic mitigation failure. Then we elaborate the latency time and an approach time estimation model to determine the effectiveness of tactical mitigation. Finally, the collision avoidance failure probability will be characterized by the endogenous failure rate of DAA system.

1) *Strategic Mitigation Failure Probability*: This part presents a conflict probability estimation model for calculating the conflict probability of UAS pair during an encounter. The trajectory error is determined by the navigation system error, the flight technical error and the wind error, which is modeled as a normally distributed to characterize the position uncertainty during the encounter. If stochastic aircraft positioning resulting from these errors falls within the defined collision zone, a strategic conflict mitigation failure will occur.

This model aims to derive an analytical solution for strategic mitigation failure probability during encounters. As shown in Fig. 2, two aircraft error covariances are combined into a single, equivalent covariance represented as M , which is assigned to the intruder. The collision envelope is assigned to the ownship so that it can be regarded as uncertainty-free. The envelope is projected along the relative velocity to form an extended collision zone, with length dependent on encounter duration. The mitigation failure probability is equal to the portion of probability density surface within this extended collision zone. Then the coordinate transformation will be presented to decouple the 3-D space and determine the analytical solution of this probability.

Let p and q represent the original and transformed coordinates. A linear coordinate transformation is $q = Tp$, where T is a transformation matrix which needs to be determined. If $W = T^{-1}$, then $p = Wq$. In the transformed coordinate system, the combined error covariance is $Q = TMT^T$, where the combined error covariance M can be represented

Fig. 2. Transformed Encounter geometry.

as $M = LL^{-1}$ according to Cholesky decomposition and L is lower triangular. Let H represent the orthogonal rotation matrix, so $HH^T = I$, if $H = TL$, then:

$$Q = TL(TL)^T = HH^T \quad (6)$$

Through coordinate transformation, the error ellipsoid is converted to the standard form of a unit sphere that can be decoupled, and the circular cylinder becomes an elliptical cylinder. Given constant altitude during encounters, horizontal and vertical motions are independent, enabling transformation decoupling into 2-D horizontal and vertical conflict probabilities via scaling, as shown in Fig. 2. Then we calculate the analytic solutions for the two directions, the total probability is the product of them because of the independence.

For the horizontal probability, firstly, using the rotation matrix H mentioned in Eq. (6) to rotate the transformed coordinate system, so that the relative velocity Δv is the x-direction of the coordinate system. The new relative velocity after the coordinate transformation $\Delta \tilde{v} = T\Delta v = HL^{-1}\Delta v$, and the partial velocity $\Delta \tilde{v}$ in the transformed coordinate system can be represented as $\Delta \tilde{v} = L^{-1}\Delta v = [\Delta v_x, \Delta v_y]^T$. According to $HH^T = I$, the rotation matrix H can be represented as:

$$H = \frac{1}{\|\Delta \tilde{v}\|} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta v_x & \Delta v_y \\ -\Delta v_y & \Delta v_x \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

Then, determining the integral expression of the 2-D conflict probability and calculating the upper and lower bounds. The boundary on the y-axis is the maximum and minimum value of the elliptical boundary. Let Δy_{pc} , Δy_{qc} represent the boundary distance of y-axis in the original and transformed coordinate systems, then: $\|\Delta y_{pc}\| = \|W\Delta y_{qc}\| = 2 \cdot R_{en}$, this equation can be squared according to:

$$W^T W = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 & x_2 \\ x_2 & x_3 \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

where x_1, x_2, x_3 are matrix elements.

Setting the discriminant of that quadratic equation to zero and solving for Δy_c . The boundary distance of x-axis Δx_c is equivalent to the distance of the aircraft pair flying during encounter, as shown in Eq. (9):

$$\begin{cases} \Delta y_c = \pm 2 \cdot L_{en} \sqrt{x_1 / (x_1 x_3 - x_2^2)} \\ \Delta x_c = d_{sr} = \Delta v \cdot t_{warning} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where the d_{sr} is the relative distance between two aircraft in 25s. The horizontal probability P_{hor} can be expressed as follows by secondary decoupling:

$$P_{hor} = \int_{q_0}^{q_0 + \Delta x_c} p(x) dx \int_{-\Delta y - \frac{\Delta y_c}{2}}^{-\Delta y + \frac{\Delta y_c}{2}} p(y) dy \quad (10)$$

where q_0 is the initial distance between the aircraft in the transformed coordinate system, $p(x)$ and $p(y)$ are standard normal distributions.

For the vertical probability, is the value of one dimension normal distributed over the conflict zone:

$$P_{ver} = \int_{\frac{-H_{en} - \Delta z}{\sigma_3}}^{\frac{H_{en} - \Delta z}{\sigma_3}} p(z) dz \quad (11)$$

where Δz is the z-coordinate of the intruder with respect to the ownship, σ_3 is the standard deviation of error in the z-axis direction, $p(z)$ is standard normal distribution.

Overall, the conflict probability during encounter (the strategic mitigation failure) is:

$$P_{ST}^{cop} = P_{hor} \cdot P_{ver} \quad (12)$$

2) *Tactical Mitigation Failure Probability*: After strategic mitigation fails, the ownship must perform tactical mitigation against intruders. The probability assessment of LOWC comprises two steps: firstly, modeling latency time through normal distribution by summarizing the process of tactical mitigation. Secondly, building a maximum approach time estimation model to calculate the minimum maneuvering distance and the maximum allowed flight time between receiving warning and performing maneuver. Tactical mitigation failure is determined when latency time exceeds the maximum approach time, indicating unavoidable LOWC regardless of maneuvers, as formulated in Eq (13):

$$P_{TC}^{cop} = 1 - \phi(t_{ap}) \quad (13)$$

where $\phi(t)$ is the cumulative distribution function of latency time, the variable t_{ap} represents the maximum approach time from warning reception to latest maneuver execution.

The first step is to determine the cumulative distribution function of latency time according to tactical mitigation process, as shown in Fig. 3, which can be summarized into three steps. Specifically, after receiving strategic mitigation failure, the USSP generates and transmits appropriate avoidance instructions to the ownship. Following instruction reception, the pilot responds to the specified maneuver to prevent LOWC. Latency time is defined as the cumulative duration of three sequential phases: separation computation, instructions communication, and response implementation. Assuming μ_{sep} , μ_{com} , μ_{pil} stand for the expectations of them and σ_{sep} , σ_{com} , σ_{pil} represent standard deviations, the values have shown in Table I according to Ref [16]. The latency time is subject to a normal distribution with exception $\mu_{ta} = \mu_{sep} + \mu_{com} + \mu_{pil}$ and deviation $\sigma_{ta} = \sigma_{sep} + \sigma_{com} + \sigma_{pil}$, the cumulative distribution function is:

Fig. 3. The general process of tactical mitigation.

$$\phi(t) = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{t - \mu_{ta}}{\sqrt{2}\sigma_{ta}} \right) \right) \quad (14)$$

TABLE I. TACTICAL MITIGATION LATENCY PARAMETERS

Parameters	Separation	Communication	pilot+ heading	pilot+ altitude
μ (mean)	6.9	2.76	4.77	2.63
σ (deviation)	2.45	1.18	3.11	1.91

The second step is to determine the approach time t_{ap} . Obviously, the shorter distance required for a ownship to perform avoidance maneuvers, the longer it is allowed to flight after receiving warning, so it is necessary to calculate the minimum maneuvering distance.

The proposed maximum approach time estimation model incorporates multiple maneuvers, such as heading and altitude adjustments, to enhance the objectivity of assessment results and extend its applicability to 3D space. The maneuver corresponding to the shortest distance is regarded as the optimal maneuver, so the distance is considered as the minimum maneuvering distance L_m , and the allowable flight time is considered as the maximum approach time t_{ap} . The Fig. 4, Fig. 5 show the processes of heading and altitude adjustment with the collision envelope centered on intruder, the model is based on a coordinate system with the Y-axis as the north-direction and the X-axis as the reference base direction.

For heading adjustment, it is considered that the aircraft can take the maximum inclination angle φ_{max} to make a turn, then the maximum lateral turn overload n and the minimum turn radius R_{turn} can be calculated from Eq. (15), in that ω is the angular velocity, v_l is the relative linear velocity.

$$\begin{cases} ng = g \cdot \tan(\varphi_{max}) \\ R_{turn} = \frac{v_l}{\omega} = \frac{v_l^2}{ng} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

When the trajectory of the ownship turning with the minimum radius R_{turn} is tangent to the collision envelope, as shown in Fig. 4, the distance of the ownship from the intruder L_m^h is defined as the minimum maneuvering distance under the heading adjustment. Assuming the heading angle of relative velocity v_3 is θ , the azimuth of two aircraft is β , so the angle between azimuth and relative velocity can be obtained by $\beta_1 = |\beta - \theta|$. Then the minimum maneuvering distance L_m^h can be calculated from a triangle with the top angle is γ_1 , the top angle varies according to the θ , if $\theta > \beta$, then $\gamma_1 = \pi/2 + \beta_3$, if $\theta \leq \beta$, then $\gamma_1 = \pi/2 - \beta_3$. In this triangle, L_m^h can be obtained referring to the cosine theorem:

$$\cos\gamma_1 = \frac{R_{turn}^2 + L_m^h{}^2 - (R_{turn} + L_{en})^2}{2R_{turn} \cdot L_m^h} \quad (16)$$

Fig. 4. The process of heading adjustment.

Fig. 5. The process of altitude adjustment.

For altitude adjustment, it is considered that the aircraft will rise quickly at the maximum climb speed v_{3z}^{max} to avoid LOWC with intruder, assuming that the horizontal relative velocity v_{3xy} remains constant during climbing, the climb angle α can be calculated by $\alpha = \arctan(v_{3z}^{max}/v_{3xy})$.

In the Fig. 5a, L' indicates the shortest distance to collision envelop, Δh indicates the altitude different between ownship and intruder. In the right triangle, the L' can be calculated from Eq. (17). In the Fig. 5b, the length of the position line between aircraft and intruder is exactly the minimum maneuvering distance L_m^a , this value is shown in Eq. (17).

$$\begin{cases} L' = (H_{en} + \Delta h) \cdot \frac{v_{3xy}}{v_{3z}^{max}} \\ \cos(|\beta - \theta|) = \frac{L_m^a{}^2 + L'^2 - R_{en}^2}{2L' \cdot L_m^a} \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

Based on the allowable flight distance obtained by the above maneuvers, the approach time t_{ap} can be calculated from Fig. 6, which expresses the positional relationship between the ownship and an intruder.

The relationship between the two velocity vectors is a triangular, in which the direction of relative velocity θ can be obtained. The relationship between relative distance and allowable flight distance can also be described by the triangle. The relative distance L_{re} between the aircraft and an intruder and the minimum maneuvering distance L_m is known, so the remaining angle γ_2 can be calculated by Eq. (18):

$$\gamma_2 = \arcsin\left(\frac{L_{re}}{L_m} \cdot \sin(\theta - \beta)\right) \quad (18)$$

The cosine theorem is then used to calculate the allowable flight distance x_f :

$$x_f = \sqrt{(L_m^2 + L_{re}^2 - 2L_m L_{re} \cos[\pi - (\gamma_2 + \theta - \beta)])} \quad (19)$$

Fig. 6. Positional relationship of ownship and intruder.

Obviously, the allowance flight distance x_f is a function of the minimum maneuver distance L_m , so maximum allowable approach time t_{ap} can be expressed as:

$$t_{ap} = \frac{\max\{x_f(L_m^h), x_f(L_m^a)\}}{v_3} \quad (20)$$

where $x_f(L_m^h)$ and $x_f(L_m^a)$ represent the minimum maneuvering distance under different strategies. v_3 represents the relative velocity between two aircraft.

3) *Collision Avoidance Failure Probability*: After tactical mitigation fails, the ownship must avoid collisions with intruders, which is mainly dependent on DAA devices. We consider collision avoidance failures P_{CA}^{cop} as the risk ratio of DAA systems, these probabilities have been bounded by the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) standard [17], which is a specification for DAA system performance requirements for small UAS. We use the maximum value of the standard as the collision avoidance failures P_{CA}^{cop} , which is 0.18 for the intruder equipped with transponder.

B. MAC Probability Assessment for non-Cooperative UAS

Beyond cooperative UAS, the ownship may face another risk of illegal intrusions from non-cooperative UAS. Due to the plans and trajectories of intruding UAS cannot be easily determined, it is difficult to calculate the conflict probability numerically as the above method. While the gas model offers a solution by simulating air molecule distribution to quantify UAS collision risks from an airspace perspective. The traditional gas model only assesses risk based on the positional distribution of air molecules without considering the mobility of them, which is obviously not consistent with the motion characteristics of aircraft. Therefore, we propose a dynamic gas model by considering the velocity of ownship.

The dynamic gas model first establishes the airspace occupied by ownship during the flight, which is determined by the DWC envelope, the velocity of ownship, and the flight time. Then this model considers that intruder's position follows a uniform distribution during the ownship's mission execution, and there is no movement trend within an instant. The procedure mitigation will be regarded as a failure if intruder enters the occupied airspace, as shown in Fig. 7, where red dots are conflicting intruders and green dots represent non-conflicting intruders. The occupied airspace can be represented as:

$$A_{oc} = 2\pi(L_{en})^2(2H_{en} + v_1 \cdot t_{mission}) \quad (21)$$

where v_1 and $t_{mission}$ represent the velocity and the flight time of ownship.

Fig. 7. The dynamic gas model for non-cooperative UAS.

The procedural mitigation failure of non-cooperative UAS can be calculated from Eq. (22), where N_{uas} represents the estimated total number of non-cooperative UAS in a certain period, which can be obtained by analyzing historical data. f_{in}^j is used to determine whether the j -th intruder has a collision risk, when the intruder is in the occupied airspace $f_{in}^j = 1$, otherwise $f_{in}^j = 0$.

$$P_{pc}^{non-cop} = \frac{\sum_1^{N_{uas}} f_{in}^j}{N_{uas}} \quad (22)$$

C. MAC Probability Assessment for Manned Aircraft

The airport area is a strictly controlled area, but given human negligence or untimely opening of corridors, there is still the possibility of intrusion by aircraft. As the range of ownship activity is almost under 1000 meters, a collision is most likely to occur during the approach and departure phases of manned aircraft, it is necessary to refer to the approach and departure procedure and the layout of the airport runways to set up an alert area, which can be called the SID and STAR area. If the flight trajectory of ownship accidentally passes through this area, it is necessary to judge whether there is a collision risk based on the airport's operation information, which is the procedural mitigation failure probability assessment. Then the maneuver instruction is issued to ownship to guide the avoidance, this is the tactical mitigation measure.

1) *Procedure Mitigation Failure Probability*: Unlike non-cooperative UAS, the approach and departure of a manned aircraft strictly follow a specific flight plan with fixed route. The distribution of manned aircraft inside the flight routes can be considered as random due to the uncertainty of daily flight plans, similar to air molecules, so we establish a dynamic gas model based on the structure of approach and departure routes to assess the risk when ownship enters the SID and STAR area, i.e., the procedural mitigation failure probability.

Fig. 8 illustrates the dynamic gas model for manned aircraft, where the ownship is considered as a mass wrapped in a combined envelope, the volume is the sum of the respective envelope of two aircraft, a manned aircraft is considered as an air molecule obeying a uniform distribution on a fixed flight route. The area swept by the ownship at a certain time with the combined envelope can also be regarded as a cube and we call it occupied airspace. Then the length of approach and departure routes at collision risk should be determined, that is, the part that is in the occupied airspace. This can be obtained by identifying the intersections of the approach and departure

Fig. 8. The dynamic gas model for manned aircraft.

routes with the cube occupied airspace and calculating the distance between them.

Assuming the number of runways of the airport is m , the total number of manned aircraft in runway j during a certain period is N_{man}^j , the procedural mitigation failure of manned aircraft can be calculated from Eq. (23):

$$p_{cop} = 1 - \prod_{j=0}^m \left(1 - N_{man}^j \cdot \frac{S_{oc}^j}{S_j} \right) \quad (23)$$

where S_{oc}^j is the lengths of runway j in occupied airspace, S_j is the total length of runway j .

2) *Tactical Mitigation Failure Probability*: When the procedural mitigation with manned aircraft fails, the ownship immediately takes appropriate actions to avoid the SID and STAR area. Due to the large speed of manned aircraft, the effect of altitude adjustment is not obvious, so the ownship mainly uses the heading adjustment to avoid entering the SID and STAR area to mitigate the MAC risk with manned aircraft. This process is similar to that shown in Fig. 6, and the relevant model has been described in detail in section III-A, so this section does not go into too much detail.

IV. ILLUSTRATIVE EXAMPLE

This section will explain how the proposed MAC assessment method can be applied, using illustrative examples encompassing a real-world environment. There are four representative scenarios in this environment, including airport intrusion, non-cooperative UAS intrusion, cooperative UAS simultaneous operations, and integrated operations.

A. Real-world environment description

A typical urban area ($16km \times 16km$) is selected, including the airport SID and STAR area. The ownship in this environment is selected as EHang 216, and the intruder is DJI Mavic 3, whose performance parameters have shown in Ref [18]. In order to define the spatial position and velocity direction of aircraft, the aerodrome reference point (ARP) of airport is regarded as the reference point of the whole environment, and the east-direction is taken as the reference base direction. The flight information of UAS is characterized by the horizontal separation (hs), azimuth(β), vertical separation relative to the reference point(vs), and the velocity direction (θ).

The environment of the case study is shown in Fig. 9, where the gray range represents the SID and STAR area, the flight in this area may pose a collision to the manned aircraft, and the rest are areas where UAS are allowed to operate. The

Fig. 9. A typical real-world scenario designed for the study.

TABLE II. SPECIFICATION OF FLIGHT PLANS FOR MISSIONS.

Mission	β (deg)	h_s (m)	v_s (m)	θ (deg)	time (s)	speed (m/s)
Mission 1	170	6000	70	20	700	15
Mission 2	180	9000	100	0	500	15
Mission 3	230	7000	100	20	630	15

ownership requiring MAC probability assessment will carry out three missions, mission one with a route through the SID and STAR area, mission two entirely inside the permissible area, and the last mission spans all areas of this environment and is used to assess the overall MAC probability from all types of aircraft. The flight plans for the missions are shown in Table II, and the MAC probability of which will be assessed.

B. Intrusion scenarios for multi-type of aircraft

1) *Airport intrusion scenario*: The scenario focuses on the SID and STAR areas to evaluate the MAC probability between UAS and manned aircraft in Mission 1. The feature of alert airspace is shown in Fig. 10, which is a polygon associated with the precision approach and departure procedure. The structural parameters are related to different runways and their orientations, the angle of glide slope, as well as the UAS altitude limit (set at 1000 ft). Based on airport data, the lengths, directions, and distances between two runways are obtained. Commercial aircraft operating within the terminal airspace typically follow fixed flight paths with minimal deviation, the combined collision envelope centered on the manned aircraft forms an extended collision area around the flight route, which consists of the DWC envelope and the size of the manned aircraft (the radius is 0.56 km and the height is 200 m with reference to Ref [19]).

The probability of procedural mitigation failure is affected by the area swept by ownship with a combined collision envelope, as well as the take-off frequency of manned aircraft. In this paper, the release interval for a single aircraft is defined as 2 minutes with reference to the wake turbulence interval standard and the average speed of civil aviation aircraft in the take-off phase. The probability of tactical failure is related to

Fig. 10. Diagram of SID and STAR area (top view).

the distance from the SID and STAR area. Table III records the MAC probability with manned aircraft during mission 1.

Mission 1's trajectory has a fixed overlap with the SID and STAR areas, and the time spent within these areas is constant. With a consistent release interval for manned aircraft, the procedural mitigation probability remains steady at 0.413 for the entire mission, as shown in Table III. To illustrate the tactical mitigation process, the mission is divided into 10-second intervals. Initially, the ownship maintains a high probability of successful tactical mitigation due to its distance from the airport. As the aircraft approaches the SID and STAR areas, the failure probability gradually increases. After 51 seconds, when the ownship is fully within the area, tactical mitigation is no longer effective, and the MAC probability depends solely on procedural mitigation. After 521 seconds, the tactical mitigation failure probability drops to zero as the ownship exits the SID and STAR area, and there is no collision risk with manned aircraft in this phase.

2) *Non-cooperative UAS intrusion scenario*: According to the dynamic gas model for non-cooperative UAS, the $P_{non-cop}$ is mainly related to the mission execution time as well as the intrusion frequency of non-cooperative UAS. Assuming that the non-cooperative UAS will not appear in the aerodrome alert airspace, so the mission 2 is used to demonstrate the MAC assessment result with non-cooperative UAS. This paper defines the intrusion frequency of corresponding airspace as 10 times a year. Since the spatial position of intruders in the model is random, the experiment is repeated 1000 times and the number of intruders at risk in each experiment is counted. Fig. 11a illustrates the location distributions of non-cooperative UAS in one experiment and the positional relationship with occupied airspace swept by ownship. Finally, the MAC probability with non-cooperative UAS during mission 2 is obtained based on Eq. (22) as 1.083×10^{-6} , this value is defined as $6.498 \times 10^{-8}/30s$ for the purpose of unifying assessment unit. Since the intrusion frequency is different depending on the range of airspace, the assessment result is scalable, which can be obtained based on the specific historical data of different airspace.

3) *Cooperative UAS simultaneous operation scenario*: To explain the feasibility of the method to cope with future multiple aircraft operational environments, a cooperative UAS

TABLE III. MAC PROBABILITY WITH MANNED AIRCRAFT.

Period	0 s - 10 s	10 s - 20 s	21 s - 30 s	31 s - 40 s	41 s - 50 s	51 s - 520 s	521 s - 700 s
P_{PC}^{man}	0.4130						
P_{TC}^{man}	3.276×10^{-8}	3.455×10^{-5}	4.005×10^{-3}	0.1156	0.5655	1	0
P_{man}	1.353×10^{-8}	1.427×10^{-5}	2.063×10^{-3}	4.776×10^{-2}	0.2336	0.4130	0

Fig. 11. The scenario of MAC probability assessment with non-cooperative UAS and cooperative UAS.

high-density operation scenario was designed around mission 2 as shown in Fig. 11b, which includes 8 UAS, whose flight directions are shown with the arrows. Considering the visual presentation of MAC probability assessment results, the spatial positions and velocity directions of 8 UAS are specifically designed to allow for a proximity or overlap point with the ownship trajectory on a spatio-temporal scale.

The assessment of P_{cop} takes into account the spatial position of aircraft pairs, the uncertainty in the position, and the information transmission latency, etc. The P_{TC}^{cop} and P_{TA}^{cop} posed by each UAS to the ownship are assessed in chronological order, and these values vary over time, which are shown in Fig. 12. The figure categorizes risks with a probability below 1×10^{-7} as unlikely and those above 0.99 as inevitable. As the UAS approaches the ownship, both P_{TC}^{cop} and P_{TA}^{cop} gradually increase, reaching a maximum probability of 1 when the UAS enters the ownship's collision envelope. Conversely, when the aircraft are moving apart, no avoidance maneuvers are necessary, eliminating the risk of tactical mitigation failure.

Combining P_{TC}^{cop} , P_{TA}^{cop} and P_{CA}^{cop} obtained from the risk ratio of DAA devices in section III-C, the real-time MAC probability can be calculated during mission execution, as shown in Fig. 12. Overall, by assessing the MAC probability of each UAS, the ownship can promptly identify intruders that may pose a remarkable threat and thus take the appropriate collision avoidance measures in advance.

C. Integrated operation scenario

The ownship may face MAC risks from multiple types of aircraft in integrated operation scenario, such as cooperative UAS, non-cooperative UAS, and manned aircraft. This section will explain the assessment process of overall MAC probability based on all assessment models in this paper. Fig. 13 describes a integrated operational scenario containing

Fig. 12. Mitigation failure probability with cooperative UAS at each phase.

eight cooperative UAS causing conflicts against the ownship with known positions and trajectories, non-cooperative UAS randomly appearing in the course of the ownship's mission with accessible positions and unknown velocities, and manned aircraft flying along a fixed SID and STAR procedure.

The final assessment results are shown in Fig. 14. It can be seen that, while in the first 100s of the mission, the overall MAC probability is mainly determined by the cooperative UAS due to the fact that the ownship is relatively far from SID and STAR area. Between 100s and 400s, as the ownship approaches SID and STAR area, the MAC probability posed by manned aircraft begins to come to the fore, resulting in a surge in the overall MAC probability, especially near 200s, when the activities of cooperative UAS are more intensive, with several trajectories intersecting with the ownship's routes, leading to a peak in the overall MAC probability. After 400s, the ownship is detached from the activity area of cooperative UAS, and the overall probability curve almost coincides with that of manned aircraft. From the total point of view, the MAC probability of ownship is mainly caused by cooperative UAS and manned aircraft, with cooperative UAS having a major role in the intensive activity area, and non-cooperative UAS posing a relatively weak MAC risk in comparison.

Fig. 13. Integrated operation scenario with manned aircraft.

Fig. 14. MAC probability with all types of aircraft.

V. CONCLUSION AND FURTHER WORK

This study presented a method for systematically assessing MAC probability from multi-type aircraft. Based on the analysis of MAC evolution timeline, this method formulated four main barriers to prevent a procedural conflict ending in a MAC and three core timelines to describe the risk evolution. To obtain the overall MAC probability, corresponding models were developed for the main barriers, considering various external factors, fast-time computation, 3D motion, and multiple maneuver strategies. This is followed by demonstrating a real-world environment and four intrusion scenarios to illustrate the assessment process. The results show that the MAC risk posed by cooperative UAS represents a significant portion of the risks considered in these scenarios and the larger protection volumes in the strategic phase will reduce the P_{cop} , which highlights the need for SORA to address the MAC risk from cooperative UAS in addition to manned aircraft and to develop more detailed separation criteria.

There are still some limitations in this research. Firstly, this paper references the alerting logic for small UAS and the DWC volume ranges in the FAA's minimum operational performance standards (MOPS), which may not be suitable for all UAS types. In future research, it is necessary to define

the relevant assessment criteria based on various speeds and sizes of UAS, and formulate the different safety separation criteria compliant with the equivalent level of safety based on numerous assessment data. Then, this paper assumes that the aircraft remains in level flight with no change in altitude during encounter, so the risk assessment based on 3D corridor structure and multiple maneuver combinations requires further research. Finally, the MAC probability assessment is the basis of risk management in the field of UAM, which needs to be further extended and combined with the probability of a fall after a collision, and the probability of damage to property on the ground or in the air after the fall, to form a complete air-ground comprehensive risk assessment model.

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